

The scales and concept of electronegativity[†]

Dulal C. Ghosh

Department of Chemistry, University of Kalyani, Kalyani-741 235, India

E-mail : dulal@klyuniv.ernet.in

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The prevailing concepts and the scales of electronegativity are discussed and reviewed. Although the electronegativity has no quantum mechanical operator and is not an experimentally measurable property, it is a true chemical entity manifest itself and the idea is indispensable qualitative tool in physics, chemistry, biology, and geology. The problem of unit electronegativity is probably solved in favour of energy unit. It is also argued that electronegativity is not an *in situ* but an intrinsic free-atom, ground-state property. The theoretical status of electronegativity is that it is fundamental and characteristic of the internal constitution of atoms and may be considered as the third dimension of Periodic Table and seems to have a 'broken symmetry' relationship with Periodic Tables's taxonomy.

Pearson¹ and Murphy *et al.*² pointed out that the term electronegativity and its association with an electron attracting power between atoms originated with Berzelius in 1811, and its continuous use since suggests that a true chemical entity is manifest itself. This is a very old and useful concept and clearly one of the central ideas of chemistry. Since the concept and also the scale first proposed by Pauling as early as in 1932, the electronegativity has become an indispensable tool in chemistry, physics, biology, and geology. Coulson³ remarked in 1951 that the concept electronegativity has the astonishing success, which the theory has had in correlating a vast field of chemical knowledge and experience. Fukui⁴ pointed out that, in the electronic theory, the static and dynamic behavior of molecules are explained by the electronic effects that are based on nothing but the distribution of electrons in a molecule and the mode of charge distribution in a molecule can be sketched to some extent by the use of the electronegativity concept. The bond energies, polarities, and the inductive effects are some very fundamental quantities of inorganic, organic and physical chemistry, and such quantities can only be conceived in terms of electronegativity. There are many other uses as well. For example, a striking dependence of the superconducting transition temperature on electronegativity is found for both solid elements and the new high-temperature superconductors⁵⁻⁷. Lackner and Zweig⁸ pointed out that the electronegativity has led to the correlation of a vast number of important atomic and molecular properties. The quantities that have been related to the electronegativities of the elements are the screened nuclear charge seen by outer electrons, the radius of electron

clouds, and the work function of metals, the electrode potentials of elements, the bond energy and the dipole moment of molecules, and the force constants. In addition, electronegativity together with the shell structure determines the possible oxidation states of an atom. Lackner and Zweig⁸ further pointed out that the electronegativity forms the basis for much of our qualitative understanding of molecular quark chemistry.

In 1932 Pauling⁹ made a landmark contribution when he defined electronegativity. In 1939, in the first edition of "The Nature of the Chemical Bond", Pauling gave his meaning of the word *electronegativity* as "the power of an atom in a molecule to attract electrons to it". He created an empirical scale of electronegativity (EN) based on heats of formation. Since then, electronegativity has become a useful parameter in understanding, explaining, and even predicting many properties related to the energy and charge distribution in chemical bonds between hetero atoms, i.e. A-B bond. The properties include ionic character, the charge distribution, the degree of polarity, the bond dissociation energies, bond moments, force constants, and the like. Thus, the treatment of heteronuclear bonds revolves around the concept of electronegativity and the use of electronegativity to understand bond energy differences was widely appreciated. An experimental measure of "the power of atom to attract electrons to themselves" has been searched for by numerous authors over nearly 60 years. Unfortunately, electronegativity – unlike atomic number, mass, ionization energy, or electron affinity – is neither a directly measurable experimental property of an isolated atom nor it can be precisely defined¹⁰. For more that sixty years the concept of

[†]Dedicated to Professor R. P. Rastogi.

electronegativity has been modified, expanded, and debated. As in any growing body of knowledge, there is plenty of room for controversy, and no two workers will agree completely. It is of great theoretical interest today. The electronegativity of an atom can perhaps least controversially be defined as the property, which determines how the bonding electrons will become distributed between it and another atom if the two atoms become connected by a chemical bond. A number of qualitative and quantitative scales of measuring electronegativity have been proposed. But, the best method of evaluating electronegativity remains to be discovered. In so far as the electronegativity concept is an offshoot from the conception of the chemical bond, it is natural that it assumes a finer structure as the concept of valence bonding develops. It is worth mentioning that although electronegativity is definitely a fundamental periodic property of atoms, it has no quantum mechanical operator and as such a quantum mechanical calculation of electronegativity is not possible². There is no operator whose expectation value is electronegativity and periodic table is not similarly derived from Schrödinger's equation². Nevertheless Periodic Table remains the central chemical reference point and similarly, electronegativity has long been one of the most important fundamental constructs in chemistry and is part of the daily thinking pattern of most practicing chemists.

The concept of electronegativity has lured chemists and evolved through a period of sixty years obviously for quantitative definition and application. Several methods of measuring electronegativity in a qualitative and quantitative manner have been proposed. A number of scales have been suggested but the attempts to refine electronegativity theory are not yet sufficiently complete to enable a verdict to be reached on their efficacy, one might reasonably expect that a clearer understanding of electronegativity property will be gained with their further development. However, despite considerable efforts expended to establish a clear definition and a commonly acceptable scale, there has been no agreement on which scale provides the best description of electronegativity. After so many approaches, there is some confusion as to what physical picture corresponds to the term electronegativity¹¹. Despite innumerable efforts, electronegativity remains a practical qualitative guide. However, recent development of the density functional theory has animated and brought again into attention the old chemical idea of electronegativity¹²⁻¹⁴. The density functional theory, DFT seems to evolve an absolute fundamental definition of electronegativity and suggests an absolute scale of its measurement. Rationalization of a large body of scattered information often dements the enunciation of qualitative principles. The electronegativity equalization

principle of Sanderson¹⁵ is one such popular electronic structure principle. The old electronegativity equalization principle of Sanderson¹⁵ finds justification in terms of the density functional underpinning of the concept and definition of electronegativity.

Each and every scale of electronegativity attempts to allot a number against each element in the Periodic Table. These numbers are thought to reflect the tendency of atoms to attract electrons when bonded. Each scale stems from a particular concept and philosophy of manifestation of the electronegativity property. In this short review we shall address the following salient points in the subjectmatter of electronegativity, viz. (i) The important scales of electronegativity, (ii) The proper unit of electronegativity, (iii) The prevailing concepts and definitions electronegativity, (iv) Whether electronegativity is 'intrinsic' or 'in situ' property ?, (v) The status of electronegativity as a fundamental theoretical quantity. (Electronegativity, the third dimension of Periodic Table).

The important scales of electronegativity

Innumerable works of chemists from abundance of chemical observation have filled up the field of electronegativity. Chemists have been able to derive ingenious concepts and scales of electronegativity that have proved their usefulness in predicting and systematizing chemical facts. In principle, pure chemical knowledge and experience allow a reasonable estimation of electro-negativity character of atoms, yet translation of that knowledge into some numerical indexing has been the target of innumerable workers. Despite the many variations and extensions of the basic idea, Pauling's original definition as "the power of an atom in a molecule of attract electrons to itself"⁹ continues to reflect in the effort of chemists in designing a scale of measurement of the property – the electronegativity. All concepts and related scales fall into three categories¹⁶. The first one is exemplified by the spirit of the original Pauling^{9,17} definition : electronegativity shall be a number ascribed to each element in the Periodic Table. These numbers are thought to reflect the tendency of atoms to attract electrons when bonded and are derived from various experimental data. The most important Mulliken¹⁸ definition was an extension of this concept to molecules but did not alter its basic foundation. Gordy¹⁹ and Sanderson¹⁵ are of this group. There are many others in this group. The second approach to electronegativity measurement has been introduced by Iczowski and Margrave²⁰ but was earlier suggested by Pritchard and Sumner²¹, electronegativity has been defined as a derivative of some hypothetical energy function. The electronegativity of this approach is called differential elec-

tronegativity. The recent work by Parr *et al.*¹²⁻¹⁴ has flourished with a rigorous definition of the differential electronegativity, identified with the negative chemical potential of electrons. It is worthwhile to mention that the density functional theory provides with absolute definition of electronegativity. There is other absolute conceptual approach to the electronegativity measurements and these may be grouped in third approach. The important scales mentioned and listed below :

1. Pauling's^{9,17} thermochemical scale.
2. Mulliken¹⁸ scale based on ionization potential and electronegativity.
3. Allred-Rochow²² scale based on estimated effective nuclear potential and covalent radii.
4. Gordy's¹⁹ scale based on number of electrons in the valence shell of atom and covalent radius.
5. Sanderson's¹⁵ scale based on covalent radius.
6. Phillips²³ scale based on dielectric properties.
7. Quantum defect electronegativity scale of St. John-Bloch²⁴.
8. Zhang²⁵ scale based on ionization energies and covalent radius.
9. The scale of Luo *et al.*^{26,27} based on the number of valence electrons in the bonding atom and the covalent radius of the atom.
10. Electronegativity scale of Nagle²⁸ based on atomic polarizability.
11. Electronegativity scale of Allen²⁹ based on the average of one-electron energy of the valence-shell electrons in ground state free atom.
12. Electronegativity scale of Lackner and Zweig⁸ for 'quark' elements.
13. The density functional view point and absolute scale of electronegativity of Parr¹²⁻¹⁴.
14. The Boyd and Edgecombe's³⁰ scale based on electron density and atomic radii.

Although the list is not exhaustive, we have cited the scales which are most important. Their conceptual basis and origin are different and the units are different. However, we do not discuss the comparative merit of scales and none is judged from the quantum mechanical viewpoint. Some of the scales of measurement of electronegativity cited above have sound theoretical basis, viz. depends on the fundamental orbital energies of isolated atom, density functional theories, spectroscopy theory etc. There are scales, which are empirical and utilize experimental quantities such as enthalpies of formation, covalent radii etc. However, we must mention out that Pauling's scale is not quantum mechanically viable² and the unit of measurement of this scale, the square-root of energy, represents no physically determinable quantity. Each scale has its advantages and disadvantages, adherents and detractors. There is a maxim that when there are many treatments for a disease, none of them is completely adequate. This same idea could be applied to electronegativity in view of the many attempts to define and quantify it. But the electronegativity concept has made serious inroad in chemistry, physics and shaping the pattern of physical and chemical thinking. Thus one may conclude, so far as the proper definition and scale of measurement of electronegativity is concerned, the last word has undoubtedly not yet been said on the subject.

The proper unit of electronegativity

The fundamental question arises what is the unit of the quantity representing electronegativity. After so many approaches, there is confusion as to what physical picture corresponds to the term electronegativity. The confusion is also manifest in the question of what should be the unit of electronegativity. It is difficult to understand the meaning of the quantity if one does not know in what units it is to be expressed. Each scale has its own unit and units of different scales are different and as such they are not comparable to each other. To make the position self-evident that the various scales suggest various different units of measurement of the same and one property, the electronegativity, we have

Table 1. Units of electronegativity

Pauling	$(\chi_A - \chi_B) = 0.208 [D(AB) - 1/2\{D(A_2) + D(B_2)\}]^{1/2}$	(Energy) ^{1/2}
Mulliken	$\chi = 1/2 (I + A)$	Energy
Allred and Rochow	$\chi = e^2 Z_{\text{eff}} / r_{\text{cov}}^2$	Force
Gordy	$\chi = e Z_{\text{eff}} / r_{\text{cov}}$	Energy/electron
Sanderson	Ratio of av. electron density to that of corresponding rare gas atom	Dimensionless
Parr	$\chi = -\mu = -(\partial E / \partial N)_v$	Energy/electron
Allen	$\chi_{\text{spec.}} = (m\varepsilon_p + n\varepsilon_s) / (m + n)$	Average one-electron energy

quoted here the units of a few scales (Table 1).

As shown in Table 1, the electronegativities obtained by different investigators have different units. Obviously, the absolute numerical values of quantities having different units are not comparable, because they represent conceptually different entities. Iczkowschi and Margrave²⁰ argued that it would be desirable to have a defining equation based clearly on a physical concept that is in harmony with definition of electronegativity and to clarify the question of unit. According to the analysis of Iczkowski and Margrave²⁰, the units of electronegativity should be energy per electron. Recently Allen²⁹ has taken up the question at length as to what should be the units of electronegativity and has put forward convincing argument to establish that the electronegativity is the third dimension of Periodic Table and the unit of electronegativity shall be energy.

Electronegativity equalization principle

Sanderson¹⁵, from an intuitive consideration, enunciated his "electronegativity equalization principle". This is one of the most interesting and useful contributions to the concept of electronegativity. The idea 'electronegativity equalization' acts during the process of formation of stable bond. Very simply it postulates that when two or more atoms, initially different in electronegativity unite, their electronegativities become equalized at some intermediate value in the molecule. The intermediate electronegativity in the molecule is taken as the geometric mean of the electronegativities of all the atoms before combination. The driving force for the equalization is easily pictured as follows: electrons in a stable covalent bond must be equally attracted to both nuclei. If they were not, they would move until this equilibrium condition is met. If the two atoms are initially of different electronegativities, their bonding orbitals are necessarily of different energies. Therefore, the process of bond formation must provide a pathway by which these energies can become equalized. Such a pathway can be based on the fact that the electronegativity of an atom must decrease as that atom acquires an electron or must increase as it loses an electron. Charge exchange in bond formation thus appears to result in a state of uneven electron sharing but even electron attraction.

The density functional approach¹²⁻¹⁴ to the problem of electronegativity seems to have placed the electronegativity equalization principle of Sanderson on a sound theoretical basis and has given a new dimension to this concept. Using density functional theory, Parr *et al.*¹²⁻¹⁴ showed that any chemical system, atom, radical, ion, or molecule, is characterized by a quantity, μ , called electronic chemical poten-

tial. It is constant everywhere (i.e. global) in the system and measures the escaping tendency of the electrons in the system. It is a property of the equilibrium system only and, hence, of ground states. It enters the density functional approach as Lagrange multiplier from the calculus of variation¹²,

$$\mu = [(\delta E[\rho]/\delta \rho)_v] \quad (1)$$

The equation refers to the functional dependence of E and μ on ρ , and E is the electronic energy, v the potential due to fixed nuclei and ρ the electron density. The alternative definition of μ is

$$\mu = (\delta E/\delta N)_v \quad (2)$$

where N is the number of electrons and E the energy, v the potential due to the fixed nuclei.

Parr *et al.*¹² made significant contribution in the history of evolution of the scale and concept of electronegativity that they made an identification that χ , the electronegativity, is the negative of chemical potential, i.e.

$$\chi = \mu = -(\delta E/\delta N)_v = -[(\delta E[\rho]/\delta \rho)_v] \quad (3)$$

If two systems C and D are brought together, electrons will flow from lower χ to that of higher χ until the chemical potentials become equal. There is energy lowering due to electrons being transferred to lower chemical potential. To be more precise in terms of traditional meaning of chemical potential, Parr *et al.* rationalized that when two systems C and D, with μ_C different from μ_D , are put in contact, the combined system will equilibrate to a new common value of μ_{C-D} differing from either of the original value. That is to say that if two species of different electronegativity or chemical potential come together to form a third, a unique common electronegativity or chemical potential results. This is what equalization of the isolated system chemical potentials. Numerically it has been found that

$$(\mu_{C-D})^2 = \mu_C \mu_D \quad (4)$$

which is called the geometric mean principle of electronegativity equalization³¹ in terms of density functional theory.

The whole gamut may be summarized as follows:

According to the density functional approach of the problem of electronegativity, the electronegativity, χ of the chemical system is the negative of electronic chemical potential μ of its electronic cloud. Given the electron density function $\rho(r)$ in a chemical system and the energy functional $E(\rho)$, the electronegativity of the system in equilibrium has been identified with the negative chemical potential. The consequence of rigorous density functional formu-

lation of ground state quantum mechanics is that if free flow is allowed, electrons go from a region of high chemical potential to a region of low chemical potential until both regions have the same chemical potential value. Sanderson¹⁵ had asserted the equalization principle long ago and he also proposed a geometric mean principle. According to Parr *et al.*, the identification of the electronegativity as the chemical potential appears to be unassailable.

The problem of proper concept and definition of electronegativity

The perennial question — can electronegativity be rigorously and usefully defined? Contemporary thinking centers on a quantum mechanical rationalization of chemical bonding but, unfortunately, as it is mentioned above, there is no operator whose expectation value is electronegativity².

From the discussions above it is self-evident that, in spite of the great amount of literature on the subject, no rigorous definition of electronegativity has been suggested and the lack of appropriate definition has resulted in some confusion with respect to both the physical concept represented by electronegativity and units of electronegativity. Allen³² has correctly observed that the concept of electronegativity, "the power of an atom in a molecule to attract electrons to itself", is one of the most important constructs in chemistry and has been found to be an useful tool for the correlation of a vast field of chemical knowledge and experience. But, because of its very broad applicability to so many properties of molecules and solids and the impossibility of making a laboratory measurement of bond polarity and a corresponding confusion of units have caused frustration and disappointment throughout the chemical community. The past sixty years has seen confusion and profusion of differing scales, which has led to the conclusion that electronegativity, χ , is an inherently fuzzy, low-information content concept. It is thought to be indefinable in principle¹⁰. Allen and Knight¹⁰ have tried to rationalized the problem — why it is so difficult to define electronegativity, χ , more fundamentally in the light of "broken symmetry"³³. Anderson³³ pointed out that the constructionist hypothesis breaks down when confronted with the twin difficulties of scale and complexity. The paradigm of 'broken symmetry' or failure of reductionist's hypothesis may be invoked to address the problem of defining electronegativity properly. Periodic Table is a molecular and solid-state taxonomy, which belongs to the set of concepts immediately above physics in the complex hierarchy of science. Even though we know the physics of the atoms that make up the Periodic Table we cannot make physical measurement of its ability to chemically organize bonding trends in molecules and solids. The problem is another

example of reductionist/constructionist philosophy³³. Periodic Table can be explained in terms of atomic solutions of Schrödinger's equation but one cannot construct the chemist's Periodic Table from the knowledge of Schrödinger's equation. It is held by Allen and Knight¹⁰ that the key feature in solving the electronegativity puzzle has been recognition that it is part of the Periodic Table and not an *ad hoc* stand-alone quantity. However, Parr *et al.*, the proponents of density functional theory, hold that electronegativity has been properly and rigorously defined¹²⁻¹⁴. According to this group, μ or χ of the ground state of the microscopic species (atom, ion, molecule or solid) is property of the system that behaves much like the chemical potential of the macroscopic thermodynamics. The electronegativity equalization principle is the property of electronegativity. Everything follows from the density functional theory of electronic structure. Parr *et al.*¹²⁻¹⁴ hold that the density functional formulation of the quantum theory leads rigorously to the concept of χ and the principle of electronegativity equalization, well known indeed for a long time.

In situ versus intrinsic

Pauling's qualitative characterization of electronegativity as the power of an atom in a molecule to attract electrons to itself was the most deeply implanted conceptualization of this quantity in chemists' minds and the valence bond representation to visualize chemical bonding led early researchers to define electronegativity as an *in situ* molecular property. However, as early as in 1961, Iczkowski and Margrave²⁰ observed that electronegativity is a property which is characteristic of the internal constitution of an atom and electronegativity represents an intensity factor to taking away small amount of charge from the other atom to which it is bonded. In 1980, Allen and Huheey³⁴ felt the necessity of correcting a long-standing defect in the general definition of electronegativity due to Pauling. In the original formulation, Pauling emphasized "the power of an atom in a molecule to attract electrons to itself". It is pointed out by them that Pauling probably implied, but it has been generally overlooked, that seen from the position of the other atom, electronegativity is equally a manifestation of an atom's ability to retain electrons and accordingly, Pauling's frequently quoted definition should be modified: "the power of an atom in a molecule to attract or hold electrons to itself". In 1983, Lackner and Zweig⁸ opined that electronegativity is intrinsic atomic property. In 1989, Allen²⁹, while designing his scale of electronegativity emphasized that electronegativity is a free-atom, ground-state property and that it derives its meaning as an extension of the Periodic Table. Allen and Knight¹⁰ opined that *in situ* assumption is

self-defeating and this is the reason why it has been so difficult to define electronegativity. It seems that Murphy *et al.*² have conclusively established that electronegativity is an atomic property. They have also tried to point out the inner contradiction inherent in Pauling's and similar other *in situ* definitions of electronegativity. The proponents³⁵ of the density functional definition of electronegativity state that it is unequivocal that electronegativity is a definite property of the ground state of an atom or molecule. Parr³⁶ pointed out that atoms in a molecule will be, in general, a species bearing a non integral number of electrons and hence atoms in the molecules carry the electronegativity.

Status of electronegativity

We must address one more point — that status of electronegativity. Whether electronegativity is a qualitative property or a fundamental quantitative property. The concept of electronegativity and electron-attracting power of an atom bonded to dissimilar atoms are inseparable. The electron-attracting power must be stemming from the screened nuclear charge. It therefore transpires that electronegativity is a property of atomic shell structure, which also justifies the Periodic Table. It is justified that there must be a fundamental relation between electronegativity and Periodic Table. Allen^{29,37} has put forward the hypothesis that electronegativity is an intimate property of the Periodic Table and that its definition follows from this fundamental relation. The properly defined electronegativity qualifies as an intrinsic third coordinate, which completes the Periodic Table. The nuclear charge also controls the charge density distribution. The proponents¹²⁻¹⁴ of density functional theory hold that the electronegativity is a fundamental intrinsic global property of atoms and density functional formulation of the quantum theory leads to rigorous definition and concept of electronegativity. Thus it may be postulated that electronegativity is a fundamental and periodic property of elements.

Conclusion

The complete history of the electronegativity concept and scale has not been reviewed here, but we pinpoint the main developments. We have addressed here the problem — can electronegativity be defined properly? It is not an observable property and hence, no quantum mechanical operator can be constructed for its quantum mechanical evaluation. Allen believes that the proper definition and scale of electronegativity is yet to evolve. Allen further holds that electronegativity is an intimate property and the third dimension of the Periodic Table and its proper definition should follow from this relationship. Allen suggests that the concept and scale of electronegativity have a 'broken symmetry'

relationship with the Periodic Tables taxonomy. On the other hand, Parr *et al.* think that the density functional formulation of quantum theory leads rigorously to the concept of electronegativity and the principle of electronegativity equalization. Majority of workers suggest that electronegativity is not an *in situ* property developed on molecule formation rather it is an intrinsic ground state property of an atom.

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Ghosh. : The scales and concept of electronegativity

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